

EDUCATION TRANSFER KNOWLEDGE 18.

Evaluation of impact on EKT proposal
in student's professional competencies
(prospective teachers)

Project Information

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Name of Project & Project Partners

The project is called Education Knowledge Transfer (EKT 612414-EPP-1-2019-ES-EPPKA2-KA) and the project partners were a mix of university and technical partners. There were 11 partners in the project, from each of 6 EU member countries. These partners were from **two main categories**:

- Technology companies that offer e-learning resources and services
- Educational institutions who provide initial teacher training (ITE).

The educational institution partners were:

1. **University of Santiago de Compostela, Galicia, Spain**
2. **University of Plymouth, Plymouth, UK**
3. **University of Minho, Braga, Portugal**
4. **University College of Teacher Education, Vienna, Austria**
5. **Marino Institute of Education, Dublin, Ireland**

The technical partners were:

1. **Supercomputing Centre of Galicia (CESGA), Spain**
2. **Lusoinfo, Portugal**
3. **BeezNest, Belgium**
4. **Die Berater, Austria**
5. **H2 Learning, Ireland.**

1.2. General Background

The Educational Knowledge Transfer – EKT project was a **Knowledge Alliance for Higher Education initiative** which included six EU countries. There were eleven institutions with different profiles involved in the project and the type of work that they conducted fell under two main categories. The first category included technology companies that offered services and resources of e-learning, and the second category was comprised of educational institutions who were responsible for initial teacher training (ITE) in their member states.

Throughout the three years of the project, **innovative strategies were implemented by combining the expert knowledge produced via educational research and technological optimizations involved in the project.** During the pilots in each country, participating institutions had the opportunity to work with new technological strategies that supported the school placement programmes in each institution, thereby ensuring placement was seen as a significant learning experience for those involved in the project.

The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the EKT project must be acknowledged at the outset of this evaluation report, where most of the EU member states went into full lockdown and schools and universities were closed for 18 months of the project implementation timeline. However, once schools and universities opened again, pilot studies continued apace, and much was done to overcome the Covid difficulties experienced by all partners to the project.

1.3. Funding Sources

A grant of **999,272.50/eur** was awarded under Erasmus+ KA2: Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices - Knowledge Alliances.

1.4. Start & Duration of the Project

The project was of 36 months duration and commenced in November 2019 and was due to end in November 2022. However, due to the impact on Covid on the project deliverables, an extension of six months to the initial timeline was granted by the EU and the project is now due to end in April 2023.

1.5. Knowledge Exchange

As we move deeper and deeper into the knowledge economy, **knowledge exchange between university and industry partners is essential** for the development of new tools. For ongoing co-configuration and customisation of specific tools for specific purposes to happen (Victor and Boyton, 1980), we must ensure dynamic, reciprocal relationships - in other words **we must talk to each other, listen carefully and then respond with a growing understanding of each other's position**. Each partner has important knowledge that is vital to the development of a new product, but sharing this knowledge is not a one-off handover of information; it is an ongoing conversation enhanced by a deep understanding of each other's needs and interests.

In this EKT project, university partners needed to explain what was so important about placement; industry partners needed to explain about the structure of what they were creating, in order to make conversations about problems and enhancement easier.

In this EKT project, **knowledge exchange occurred as industry partners learnt about the kinds of communication that need to be facilitated during teaching placements in universities**. They learnt about who needs to communicate and when about what sort of things, what needs to be recorded and assessed and what else needs to be accessible. At the same time, university partners learned about the affordances and constraints of digital tools. Conversations between partners needed to respond in real time to ideas and concerns, and to position the tool that the industry partners were building in the wider context of other official university sites and social media.

1.6. Project Aims

Knowledge Partnerships aim to strengthen European innovation capacity and encourage innovation in higher education and collaboration with business and the wider socio-economic environment. They are therefore intended to achieve one or more of the following **general objectives** reported in this project:

- To develop new innovative and multidisciplinary approaches to teaching and learning
- To stimulate the entrepreneurial spirit and business skills of higher education teaching staff and staff in enterprises
- To facilitate the exchange, circulation and joint creation of knowledge.

The **main groups and institutions** targeted by the EKT project were:

- University lecturers and researchers of Education Sciences
- Universities (especially Faculties of Education, University Colleges of Teacher Education)
- Kindergarten, Primary and Secondary Education Schools and teachers
- Higher Education Students (European Kindergarten, Primary and Secondary Education prospective teachers) and
- E-learning companies (providers of ICT and services)

1.7. Project Objectives

The EKT project overall objective was to contribute to the modernisation of European higher education systems, promoting student-centred learning and teaching through increased support for effective cooperation between higher education institutions, enterprises and the public sector. **The specific objectives of the project included**

- **To align the response of technical companies** (in the e-learning sector) with the needs of education in Europe in order to articulate a better response to the challenges facing education today. Specifically, to align advanced e-learning tools and services with active and flexible teaching-learning methodologies, which allow better collaboration, supervision and mentoring between universities and schools in order to produce a reflexive process during the school placement timeline, for future teachers.
- **To establish co-operation between e-learning companies** (ICT and service providers) and researchers/education experts (education science faculties), to ensure innovation in higher education. In particular such co-operation allowed technical partners pilot their e-learning tools and services in real educational contexts. This also ensured they could research and develop their future uses to adapt them to educational needs in various EU partner countries.
- **To improve the quality of university training of student teachers during their professional training period** (school placement period) through the implementation of ICT services and resources, developed jointly between e-learning companies and universities. This was to be achieved through the development of flexible educational methodologies, advanced e-learning solutions that were adapted to the initial teaching processes, supporting collaboration, monitoring, and reflective learning of student teachers.

The **overall objective of the EKT project is to ensure the technological platform created can be used in other universities**, with any type of education, that include placement requirements and could also support the teaching induction period, across the EU member states in the future.

2. EVALUATION FRAMEWORK & METHODOLOGIES

The **overall aim of the evaluation plan** (O15) as devised by Marino Institute of Education (MIE) and University of Plymouth (PU) in early 2020 was to

- Design and develop methods and tools for project monitoring, quality and evaluation
- Monitor the progress of each work package and process in the project
- Evaluate intermediate and final project results, including objectives from work packages.

The **purpose of that evaluation plan** was to allow partners to monitor the project's progress and to ensure the project remained responsive to shifts in purpose and to allow all partners to have an open dialogue throughout, by providing timely information on progress and developments.

The **specific objectives of O18** were to evaluate the impact of the EKT methodology and e-learning system on the development of professional skills (collaboration, communication, self-learning, and reflection) by the project participants in each of the partner institutions.

2.1. Evaluation Plan Criteria

The evaluation plan outlined overarching criteria that all elements of the EKT project objectives should adhere to (Figure 1) and are noted here for ease of reference, as they are explained fully in O15 and O17.

Figure 1: Overall Evaluation Criteria of EKT

2.2. Quality Assurance

Three final reports were produced to evaluate the extent to which the project has met its objectives, and the quality of its outputs:

1. **016** - Evaluation of transnational meetings;
2. **017** - Evaluation of users' satisfaction and assessment of the products derived from the project;
3. **018** - Evaluation on impact of EKT proposal on students' professional competencies.

All evaluation tools created were done so in a confidential and anonymous manner (especially in relation to the questionnaires devised). The evaluation of professional skills learned as part of this project were based on Compeau and Higgins' (1995) technological self-efficacy scale, which has been proven as a valid digital competency measurement scale in recent literature (Depaepe & König, 2018; Moulding, Stewart, & Dunmeyer, 2014, Niederhauser & Perkmen, 2010, Thibaut, Knipprath, Dehaene, & Depaepe, 2018). This tool had been used successfully by the lead researcher (Egan, 2018) to evaluate pre-service teachers' confident use of various technological tools, during her PhD and subsequent post-doctoral research. This tool was applied in the EKT project to evaluate users' professional competencies for O18, in particular.

3. EVALUATION METHODS

Figure 2: Work Package 7 Objectives

WP7	Evaluation and quality plan (MIE & PU)	Achieved
O18	Evaluation on impact of EKT proposal in student & professional competencies (prospective teachers)	Yes

The methods utilised during **output 18 (O18)** are now discussed and how they were applied by each partner university. **Figure 3** demonstrates the timeline for the application of each tool, for each pilot study, in each partner university. For example, once pilot participants had completed the **SPOC (small private online course)**, they were sent a questionnaire to evaluate their satisfaction using that tool (reported in O17). These pilot participants were then invited to attend a focus group or interview and were asked for their evaluation of the combined competencies acquired using the **SPOC & EKT Platform (O18)**. This data, combined with the technological self-efficacy questionnaire noted earlier informed the results for this O18. [Annexes A and B](#) of this report provides access to the quantitative and qualitative instruments developed for the collection of evaluation data in the 5 countries.

By using a mixed methods approach to the research, the full views of EKT participants were collected. All questionnaire data were analysed using **SPSS and MS Excel**, and the interview and focus group data were analysed using **NVivo**, adhering to a thematic analysis methodology, advocated by **Braun & Clarke (2015)**. [Annex C](#) of this report provides access to the quantitative and qualitative data collected in the five countries on the basis of which the evaluation was carried out.

Figure 3: Evaluation Tools used by each Partner (O18)

4. KEY FINDINGS & RESULTS

This section will review the results of **O18** which sought to evaluate the impact of the EKT proposal on professional competencies of the future teachers (i.e., student participants) in this project. These professional competencies as set out as a matrix in document **O6: EKT Educational and Technological Framework** (Fernandez-Morante & Cebreiro et al, 2023) which is arranged as familiar concepts in consideration of the professionalisation of the workforce (professional updating, educational intervention, creativity and innovation, social and relational skills, communication, use of digital media, personal and ethical orientation, and reflection) and their associated competencies. These competencies are not easy to assess and, as outlined in O6, can be open to subjective interpretation and cultural variation. In the context of a project concerned with teaching placements in five different national systems, this flexibility and lack of precision could be considered a strength rather than a weakness, as it is easy for teacher educators from different countries to connect items in the EKT Framework with elements of their own evaluation systems.

Figure 4: EKT Teaching Competence Framework

		AREA OF COMPETENCE							
		Professional updating	Educational intervention	Creative and innovation	Social and relational	Communicative	Digital y mass media	Personnel and Ethics	Reflection, evaluation and feedback
CONCEPTUAL DESCRIPTION:		- To retrain, to maintain "employability", to constantly train oneself with regard to the demands and needs that arise in the work context.	- Transfer professional knowledge and skills to real educational scenarios and processes.	- Create new approaches and novel/innovative approaches to educational processes and scenarios. - Continuous improvement of practice.	- Creating and managing positive interaction situations in any professional or personal scenario/ situation - Contribute to maintaining a favourable climate for coexistence, learning and collaboration.	- Maintain an attitude of proximity and empathy with students, families and other professionals. - Creating and managing communication situations with empathy, receptiveness, spontaneity and clarity, fostering a climate of trust and constructive exchange with the different agents (classmates, students, families, etc.).	- Incorporate the educational possibilities of digital technologies and media into educational processes and institutions. - To guarantee the digital and media literacy of students. - Accompany and collaborate with families in their responsibility for the digital and media education of students.	- Knowing oneself, taking care of oneself and maturing personally. - Maintain an emotional balance. - Develop critical thinking. - Mainain an active commitment to identity, professional ethics and the teaching profession. - Maintain an active commitment to inclusive values and respect- promotion of diversity in all its forms. - Maintain an active commitment to equality and co-education	- Incorporate the educational possibilities of digital technologies and media into educational processes and institutions. - To guarantee the digital and media literacy of students. - Accompany and collaborate with families in their responsibility for the digital and media education of students.
	COMPETENCIES	- Ability to acquire, assimilate, use and manage new contents related to educational action. - Capacity for the selection and application of contents and resources appropriate to the living space of each student and linked to their evolutionary process.	- Ability to select, design, use and consciously manage approaches, methods, didactic situations, adapted educational programmes, techniques, psycho-pedagogical procedures, learning spaces and times, as well as the most appropriate personal, material and digital resources to dynamise, promote and motivate learning. - Ability to work in teams with the members of the educational community in collective pedagogical projects oriented from a cooperative perspective.	- Ease of adaptation to changes in the educational process, generating new learning opportunities that are original, flexible, viable and adapted to the learning needs of each student. - Ability to explore different forms of creative expression in order to develop the child's aesthetic taste and critical spirit in the creative process.	- Ability to relate and interact appropriately with pupils, parents, colleagues and other experts involved in education - Ability to manage the participation, collaboration and intervention of pupils, mothers, fathers, colleagues and other experts linked to education in educational action.	- Ability to establish effective and efficient pedagogical communication with pupils, their parents and other members of the educational community. - Ability to regulate conflicts by orienting them towards dialogic processes and towards their resolution through cooperation and negotiation.	- Safe and critical use of information society technologies (IST) in order to improve the effectiveness of In-school placement. - Appropriate use of digital sources and resources for continuous professional development and communication with the different members of the educational community. - Designing flexible scenarios and digital educational content	- Active engagement in relation to teachers' professional identity and ethics. - Ability to promote education in values with a moral basis and from a perspective of responsibility and respect.	- Ability to reflect from a positive point of view and to critically assess one's own pedagogical work and that of others, in order to contribute to the improvement of one's own and others' education. - Ability to use evaluation as a means of regulating and improving didactic action.

Nonetheless, several outputs from the EKT project can offer insights into how the development of student teachers' professional competencies might be supported by an appropriately designed and implemented placement platform. We will therefore focus here on **work package 4, creation of the EKT platform; work package 6, pilot studies in each partner countries** and the measurement of the professional digital competencies associated with use of the EKT Platform and associated contents carried out in **work package 7**. The findings for each work package are analysed according to the overarching themes of **collaboration, communication, self-learning and reflection**, which the astute reader will recognise as closely associated with the above mentioned **EKT Educational and Technological Framework (O6)**.

4.1. Work Package 4

CESGA, the lead technical partner from Spain, led on work package 4 and were tasked with creation of innovative e-learning services and resources to improve the ITE experience during school placement in schools.

Figure 5: Work Package 4

WP4	Develop and advanced e-learning system for in-school teaching practice (in-school placement) (CESGA)	Achieved
O7	Technical analysis report: Infrastructure definition and guidelines.	Yes
O8	Advanced e-learning system for in school placement	Yes
O9	Mobile app development	Yes

4.1.1. Evaluation Method – EKT Platform Live

This work package presented an alpha version (Version 1) of the EKT platform in July 22. An improved beta version (version 2) was released and went live in October 22 and the final release of the EKT platform has been live since April 2023. The final ‘mobile application’ development is complete and is available for Android devices since April 23, and can be downloaded from the Google Play store here¹.

A series of screenshots (Figure 6 to Figure 10) demonstrate what the EKT platform looks like in its current format and is accessible at <https://app.ektproject.eu/>.

Figure 6: EKT Platform Landing Page

¹<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.cesga.ektproject>

Figure 7: EKT User Features (Coordinator Dashboard)

Figure 8: EKT Platform Course Creation Area

Figure 9: Google Play Store EKT App & Smartphone home screen

Figure 10: SPOC Training Area on EKT mobile App

4.1.2. Focus Group Data

Comments from focus group participants noted the ‘ease of use’ of the EKT Platform and were particularly impressed with the way the EKT platform worked on multiple browsers, including (eventually) their Android mobile devices. As well as the obvious association with the competence to ‘make appropriate use of digital sources and resources for continuous professional development’, this was allied to a realisation of the social and relational possibilities of the platform. There was a strong message from the participants’ comments about **collaboration – and in particular collaboration through sharing resources and finding ways to make colleagues lives easier**. For example,

working with EKT project has allowed me to see that the mentors need more possibilities to collaborate in this tough exercise because the mentors are representing the university but they also need to adapt to the unique contexts of the students so the mentors that way can have opportunities to share their resources [...] so this is what our colleague has stated - the possibility that the EKT system can help with [academic mentor].

Communication was mentioned frequently by all participants to the study where, during one of the Spanish workshops, it was noted by a placement mentor that,

with this new methodology there is more coordination, therefore the practicum becomes more meaningful so to speak. There’s joint planning and there’s also ongoing communication. In the traditional practicum there was barely any communication between the school mentors and the university mentors and in this case this new methodology allows for the three players, for the students and academic mentors and school mentors, to have a better communication [placement mentor].

However, communication on a **technological platform** does not occur without a strong research design, as noted by one of the teacher mentors in the project,

It has to be designed - there should be a common path of communication amongst all the players in that strategic triangle [...] I believe that the internship period is very important, very important, not the traditional internship but what the EKT promotes [teacher mentor].

The **self-learning affordances** of the tool were also mentioned frequently by the research participants where,

I think that thanks to that we could stage our work more and we started to conduct research in a direct and explicit way, we were almost forced to reflect upon our internship period. Because we are schools within active participation, doing things and if you stay there for five hours, for example, you don’t have time to think and when you go home and you sit and down and if there is something that tells you what you have to reflect upon, what you do today, so at the end of the day this is a learning process, this is where we instruct our knowledge on or otherwise we will not achieve any improvements [student].

Finally, the EKT platform did become a **useful reflection tool** for most of the research participants in the work, where an academic mentor noted,

...this where we bring theory and practice together; this is when we reflect and that part, which is very important, is only allocated a very small amount of time, at least from our viewpoint as university lecturers, in terms of classifying those placements, following them, monitoring them and so on. So this tool is going to be very positive because we don’t have much time [academic mentor].

4.2. Work Package 6

H2 Learning, Ireland was tasked with **work package 6**, which involved creation of a pilot guide for implementation of the EKT platform in each country, and creation of an overall report on the implementation of the various pilot studies by each university partner. This work package was affected by the inability to conduct pilot studies by any partner institution during the Covid pandemic. However, once the pandemic restrictions were lifted, pilot studies were conducted in all partner universities successfully and H2 Learning achieved their work package requirements. It is worth noting that some duplication of results between **WP6 and WP7** is expected here, as the data collection tools used by all partners informed the results and findings for both work packages.

Figure 11: Work Package 6

WP6	Pilot Study (H2)	Achieved
O13	Pilot guide	Yes
O14	Pilot report	Yes

4.2.1. Evaluation Method – Results from each Partner on their Pilot Study

Output 13 was achieved in September 2021 in draft version and the final version was produced in February 2023. A full copy of the Pilot Guide is available for download here. The pilot guide is available in four EU languages and is very useful as an aid when setting up the EKT platform, and describing to users the processes, tasks, and responsibilities necessary for successful implementation of the EKT methodology and online platform.

Output 14 details the pilot reports from each of the partner countries on the EKT project. Demographic data on participation rates per country are shown in the diagrams that follow. A copy of the full Pilot Report, created by H2 Learning, is available here.

Figure 12: Overall participation numbers in the EKT piloting countries

Country	Student Teachers		Academic Coordinators	Academic Mentors	School Mentors
	Registered	Completed			
Austria	70	30	1	5	15
Ireland	9	9	1	1	0
Portugal	28	10	1	4	5
Spain	104	104	1	14	104
UK	28	28	1	10	0
Total	239	190	5	34	124

4.2.2. Quantitative Data

The EKT platform users were invited to evaluate their experiences of using the EKT platform and the following diagrams summarise the responses of those pilot participants who completed the questionnaires, in each partner institution. Hence, there were 190 pilot participants, and of these, 139 completed the questionnaire instruments.

Figure 13: Number of Pilot Participants in each Partner Country

	N	%
Austria	28	20,1%
England	12	8,6%
España-Galicia	78	56,1%
Ireland	12	8,6%
Portugal	8	5,8%
Total	139	100,0%

Figure 14: Bar Chart Pilot Participants per Country

Figure 15: Gender of Pilot Participants in each Country

Figure 16: Roles of Pilot Participants - by Country

Figure 17: Age Profile of Pilot Participants per Country

Figure 18: Roles & Age Profiles of Pilot Participants

Figure 17 details the gender breakdown of respondents to the questionnaires in each country. Of note is the predominance of female participation across all partner universities. This is not unusual and is reflective of a similar demographic profile of student teachers in many of the partner universities. This is especially evident in the Irish respondents to the questionnaire, who were all female. The age profile of the cohort is of interest, where Spanish and Irish student teachers were younger (18 to 20 years) than the Austrian, English and Portuguese (21 to 30 years) participants.

Figure 18 outlines the age profile of the members of the teaching triad, in each country. The student teacher age profile is young (18 to 30 years) which is expected. Equally, the school tutor age profile ranges from 31 to 40 years of age, as reported by each partner country. Of note, however, is that the age profile of the academic supervisor in all countries, ranges from 41 to 60 years of age. This may be reflective of the availability of academic supervisors, where in Ireland, for example, many supervisors are retired teachers and are available to conduct supervision during the day as they are not working elsewhere. This may be mirrored in other countries and is worth exploring in future research.

The age profile of participants across all partner countries is also of interest when the digital competencies of each teaching triad persona is considered. However, as the data collected was anonymous there was no way to track levels of digital competency by age profile, as individual participant responses could not be identified. However, this is an area for future research when the EKT platform is used more widely across Europe.

4.2.3. Focus Group & Interview Data

Research participants in each university were contacted by H2 Learning (WP6 lead) to ensure their views were collected as part of their pilot report. WP6 lead partner created 'use cases' of each type of user of the EKT platform and collected their opinions on the success of the platform to support their individual needs. The feedback noted by WP 6 can be categorised into the 4 main themes of collaboration, communication, self-learning, and reflection, as with all outputs of this EKT project.

4.2.4. University of Teacher Education, Vienna

In Austria, the research participants found the EKT system practical and easy to use, where the tasks for action-oriented reflection were useful during school placement. Data was also collected that noted the effectiveness of the online course and possibilities for communication and reflection, using the EKT platform. In particular, in the Austrian focus groups, the student teachers emphasised the value of peer learning and communication in the chat tool and academic mentors highlighted the value of self-study research and the reflection affordances of the platform.

4.2.5. Marino Institute of Education, Dublin

In Ireland, all participants commented on the 'communication' tools on the EKT platform, where it was noted that 'chats can occur with staff and each other to help and support our peers too' and participants liked that they could 'divide their personal and professional life using the platform' instead of using WhatsApp and other social media tools to communicate with each other, during placement. This was the single biggest win of the platform for all participants in the Irish pilot study and demonstrates the need for communication and collaboration between all partners in the placement triad, the placement teacher, the student, and the academic mentor.

4.2.6. University of Plymouth, England

In England, the main strength of involvement in the EKT project was the focus on communication during placements – as opposed to the perhaps more familiar focus on assessment and completion of tasks to demonstrate competency against the UK Department for Education's Initial Teacher Training (ITT) Core Content Framework, ultimately evidencing achievement of the Teachers Standards. This has led to enhanced understanding of the role of mentors as the 'glue' that holds the system together. This was an important result for the English partner and mirrors the results for other universities in the EKT project more widely.

4.2.7. University of Minho, Braga

In Braga, students were invited to upload documents and use the ePortfolio as a tool for reflection and communication. The pilot study in Portugal was delayed due to the pandemic and other factors, and as a result the Portuguese data belies some redundancy in the platform regarding reflection and communication, and participation was rather low. Furthermore, students were meeting their supervisors regularly, in person, and did not feel the necessity of using the platform to communicate and share documents online. Some issues related to the privacy of the communications on the platform and of the documents hosted on EKT, were also raised by the Portuguese pilot participants. These findings are similar to an increased awareness of all partners as to their GDPR obligations when dealing with data more generally.

4.2.8. University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain

In Spain, the research project was conducted over a longer period and with larger cohorts of students, and this is evident in the range and variety of data collected during their focus groups and interviews. The Spanish partner also had a larger number of academic mentors involved in their research study, and their comments are of relevance in relation to the communication, collaboration and other affordances of the EKT platform, during the pilot implementations.

The EKT system has been very successful for all placement mentors, students and co-ordinators where University of Santiago de Compostela has received requests for wider use of the EKT tool in future academic years and by other institutions. Equally, the platform has engendered a level of collaboration and joint learning among the academic mentors. There were some issues in Spain, but similar to other countries, where difficulties were experienced when trying to involve and recruit school mentors to the research project. Furthermore, clear requirements of the reflections required of students must be agreed in advance with academic and school mentors. The Spanish partner also had technological issues where integration with systems already in use in the university proved problematic from a GDPR and security point of view. However, these findings will and shall inform the next iteration of the EKT platform for the Spanish and future users of the system.

4.3. Work Package 7

Marino Institute of Education (MIE) and the University of Plymouth (PU) led on work package 7. The final requirement was O18 to evaluate the impact of the EKT proposal on students' professional competencies and is reported here specifically in relation to users' experiences collected in focus groups and questionnaire data.

Given the delayed implementation of pilot studies, this had a tangential effect on the evaluation of the SPOC and EKT Platform by users, for this work package. However, once pilot studies commenced again in each partner university, evaluation of users' satisfaction with the outputs of the EKT project occurred in a timely manner, alongside self-evaluation of technological competencies. Pilot reports from each of the partner countries were scrutinised for evidence of impact on professional competencies, supplemented by analysis of the panel discussion between students and mentors during the final conference. This work package ended in April 2023 once the final transnational partner meeting was complete.

Figure 19: Work Package 7

WP7	Evaluation and quality plan (MIE & Up)	Achieved
O15	Evaluation and quality plan	Yes
O16	Evaluation of transnational meetings	Yes
O17	Evaluation of users' satisfaction and assessment of the products derived from the project.	Yes
O18	Evaluation on impact of EKT proposal in student & professional competencies (prospective teachers)	Yes

4.3.1. Output 18 Professional Competencies

This output sought to check if the **EKT Platform** had any impact on pilot participants' **professional competencies**. The method used to collect data to assess this potential impact was the **technological self-efficacy questionnaire** as applied to the EKT Platform, as noted earlier.

There are ten technological self-efficacy statements in the original **Compeau & Higgins' instrument**, and they were adapted for the EKT environment. Recent literature notes the reliability of this tool to measure **digital confidence** and laterally **competence**, (Depaepe & König, 2018; Moulding, Stewart, & Dunmeyer, 2014; Niederhauser & Perkmen, 2010; Thibaut, Knipprath, Dehaene, & Depaepe, 2018). This tool had been used successfully by the lead researcher (Egan, 2018) to evaluate pre-service teachers' use of various technological tools, during her PhD and subsequent post-doctoral research. This tool was applied in the EKT project to evaluate users' competencies for **O18**, in particular, as noted earlier.

Pilot participants were asked to rate their levels of agreement from 1 'strongly disagree' to 5 'strongly agree' to the statements posed in the questionnaire. Statements such as "I am able to integrate the EKT platform into my placement work with minimal help", "I am able to use the EKT platform without being told how it works" and "I am able to use my knowledge of the EKT platform to help my peers" were presented to pilot participants. Qualitative focus groups were held to analyse additional professional competencies acquired during the EKT project timeline by the pilot participants.

The data reported here are from respondents to the pilot questionnaire administered in each country, after their pilot studies had completed. As such, there is a difference in the number of pilot participants reported in **work package 6** (pilot report) to the number of respondents to the questionnaire, reported here in **work package 7**.

4.3.2. Questionnaire Data from each Partner

Figure 20: Levels of Digital Confidence with EKT Platform

Figure 21: Digital Confidence Scores for EKT Platform Use

Overall, all pilot survey participants (N=139) scored positively on the **technological self-efficacy scale** as applied to the EKT Platform (Figure 20). A breakdown of the **mean score** for each statement is presented shortly but the mean score (3.69 SD .663) shows a positive outcome for **digital efficacy** of survey participants on the platform. The **median score** was 3.75 which demonstrates this positive result further. However, the Austrian survey participants record some dissatisfaction with the EKT Platform (mean 2.97). As they were early adopters of the EKT Platform, there may have been some bugs and anomalies in the alpha version of the devised platform. This data is borne out in their **qualitative comments** relating to the platform, as noted in the pilot study report.

Each statement in the full technological self-efficacy questionnaire is now presented and mean scores for each country are discussed (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Digital Self Efficacy Statements by Country - Mean Scores

Technological Self Efficacy Statements & EKT Platform - Mean Scores per Country					
Statements - Levels of Agreement 1 to 5 Likert (Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree)	Spain	Portugal	Ireland	Austria	UK
I am able to use my knowledge of the EKT platform to help my peers	3.95	3.88	4.00	2.83	3.75
I am able to Adopt and adapt the EKT platform for assignments/school placement	3.87	4.00	4.00	2.59	3.83
I am able to Integrate the EKT platform into my placement work creatively	3.51	3.88	4.00	2.17	3.75
I am able to Integrate the EKT platform into my placement work with minimal help	3.74	3.88	3.58	2.24	3.67
I am able to Search, evaluate and select appropriate technology resources within the EKT platform	3.87	4.00	3.58	2.76	3.42
I am able to Navigate the contents of the EKT platform	4.18	4.00	4.00	3.17	3.75
I am able to Use the EKT platform without being told how it works	3.32	3.63	3.33	3.28	3.08
I am able to Use the EKT platform if there were user manuals/help available	4.08	3.88	4.42	3.28	4.00
I am able to Complete a job or task using the EKT platform	3.94	4.00	3.83	3.55	3.75
I am able to Complete a job or task using the EKT platform if there were user manuals/help available	4.09	3.63	4.17	3.83	3.92
Overall Mean Scores - TSE Scores for Each Statement	3.86	3.88	3.89	2.97	3.69

The **Spanish survey participants** (n= 78) 'strongly agree' that they can navigate the contents of the EKT platform and can use the EKT platform if there were user manuals available. The **Portuguese survey participants** (n= 8) 'strongly agree' they can adopt and adapt the EKT platform for school placement and they also feel competent in their ability to complete a job or task using the EKT platform. The **Irish survey participants** (n =12) are equally competent in their ability to adopt and adapt the EKT platform for school placement and they also strongly agree that they can use the EKT platform to help their peers. In **England** (n= 12) **survey participants** only strongly agree that they can use the EKT platform if there were user manuals available. Their levels of agreement with the other 9 statements are nearer the middle of the scale. The **Austrian survey participants** (n=28) are less competent in their use of the EKT platform, but as previously noted, the timing of their pilot study may have impacted on their digital competency scores given they were first to adopt the tool.

4.3.3. Focus Group & Interview Data

Qualitative data from focus groups participants about the EKT Platform are very positive, in all countries, with messages about collaboration and communication again featuring strongly. For example:

- “The value of integration of tools is here on this platform”
- “The importance of being able to share my work with others and being able to learn from other people’s work on this platform”
- “chats can occur not only with students but also staff”
- “how much this will benefit both students and teachers in teaching and learning”
- “la posibilidad de experimentar con una herramienta diseñada para facilitar el practicum”.

As such, the EKT Platform was perceived by all as a useful and timely addition to school placement where the ‘one stop shop’ aspect of the platform was important for participants to the study.

I would like to add and remind you all that I was part of the focus group in Portugal and I remember that there was a student who mentioned this with the school mentor I have this tool, with the academic mentor I had this other tool, while here I have everything together so that all together all in one set, that sort of one-stop shop that we have here is what’s really relevant. we have one space where all of the tools are available with one click. I don’t have to track what my student has sent to me by e-mail for example. everything is available there. And for me this is a very very important function [academic mentor].

However, in some countries, pilot participants did wonder if the tool had been superseded by other more commercially available educational tools. In particular there was a concern that tools like WhatsApp and Snapchat were already widely used to support collaboration in the social sphere, and in Ireland, for example, participants noted they already used tools such as MS Teams and Moodle for placement, and participants wondered if the EKT Platform could integrate into tools they were already familiar with. For example, the timing of the release of the EKT platform for some was unfortunate, **“It can be clunky at times; the username and password issues; hard to navigate; it is not integrated with other tools that are very user friendly; it would have been great to have this two years ago when COVID hit”**. Integration into platform already in use in some Institutions, by way of an LTI for Moodle for example, was outside the remit of this EKT Project but might be something to consider in future platform developments.

Digital confidence is not, however, as widespread as perhaps might be anticipated in the younger generation of students; the EKT platform seems able to build on previously acquired ICT skills thereby benefitting from existing levels of digital confidence. Of note here in relation to the data collected is the confident use of the EKT platform is comparable to Kruger and Dunning’s (1999) seminal analysis that “skills that engender confidence are often the same skills you need to evaluate your competence in that particular domain” (p. 1121) where Kruger and Dunning suggested that often confidence did not necessarily equate to competence, in a particular field. As of April 2023, we can say that all survey participants were at least somewhat confident users of the platform.

Thematic analysis of the qualitative data suggests a number of emergent themes in relation to professional competencies where users agree that the EKT platform presents a space for collaboration and communication in particular.

With this new methodology there is more coordination, therefore the practicum becomes more meaningful so to speak. There’s joint planning and there’s also ongoing communication. In the traditional practicum there was barely any communication between the school mentors and the university mentors and in this case this new methodology allows for the three players, for the students and academic mentors and school mentors, to have a better communication [teacher mentor].

We will have to overcome the obscurantism [sic.] that has been developing for a long time and, now we can see some light from the planning with the students or with academic mentors from the University School, the communication between the three players and a final assessment and the reflection at each one of the stages of the process [teacher mentor].

This insight into improved communication via the EKT platform leading to better understanding between stakeholders was also echoed by students:

With this platform the academic mentors can have some vision in the stage of the practicum because [without EKT] what they could assess in a more objective way was that briefing we would give at the end of the period. But they did not know our internships. However, through this platform they can have a more direct communication and they can get to know our reality in the classroom and I think this is a very important part and also in terms of the final assessment of the training [student].

The affordances of the tool to promote reflective practice were also noted by participants where,

with this tool we mentors can see their reflections, their comments, their opinions and that also helps us reflect upon the work we are doing. it also helps us innovate and improve our own work in our schools. So this tool not simply a direct communication tools but also an indirect one; it is a tool that helps us improve as professionals ourselves or at least that's what I've seen [teacher mentor].

the practicum in and of itself is the summit of the students' training [...] the students can implement all the knowledge acquired here [in the university] in the schools and therefore they can realise the value of all the knowledge that we taught them [academic mentor].

With these teaching practices they can organise all of the knowledge that they've learned, and they can go even far beyond that. So this is why it is very relevant to turn this subject into a dynamic space where students have the opportunity not only of putting into practice what they have learnt but to start an interaction. this is what will make future teachers professionals who reflect upon their actions. It provides experience of improving practice; it stimulates and encourages creativity, the capacity to innovate [academic mentor].

However, it was unclear if the EKT platform would act as a tool to engender this self-learning in the future. The benefits of the SPOC for self-learning were **acknowledged strongly** by all participants and the SPOC tool was very well received by all participants, as noted in O17 report.

Generally, the EKT project has developed an awareness by all partners, of the value of the placement/practicum/teaching practice for students, academic mentors, and placement teachers. It is a time when students can walk alongside teachers, to develop a real sense of what it is like to be a teacher, thereby anticipating the move from student to professional:

This is what will make future teachers, professionals who reflect upon their actions and it helps teachers better accompany the process towards their future. This improvement through accompaniment is one of the key milestones in teaching practices. It basically involves sitting next to all of these educational stakeholders and following their daily practice, listening to their concerns, to whatever they do, this active listening that is so important when it comes to teaching [academic mentor].

That this can be mediated and supported on a technological platform as a result of this EKT project is a huge achievement for all concerned, and a timely innovation for placement practices in European countries into the future.

Future work could include measurement of users' continued engagement with the EKT Platform and their future digital self-efficacy at frequent junctures, to trace the impact of the EKT platform on users' digital competencies, over a longer timescale. Indeed, the results of this questionnaire demonstrate the positive impact of the EKT platform on the pilot participants' competencies, and their qualitative data outlines their satisfaction with the platform further.

5. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

The overall aim of the EKT project was to transfer knowledge between schools, HEIs and industry, in the context of designing a platform and associated course to support student teachers on placement. The platform and the course are the 'tangible' outcomes of this transfer of knowledge, and these have been evaluated and reported in output O17 evaluation of users' satisfaction. The project also sought to consider the extent to which the EKT platform and associated activities offered opportunities for the development of students' professional skills. In the data presented in this report (O18), there is **strong evidence** of the increase in important professional skills clearly related to EKT Pedagogical and Technological Framework (O6) of familiar concepts of professional updating, educational intervention, creativity and innovation, social and relational skills, communication, use of digital media, personal and ethical orientation and reflection) and their associated competencies. In the report we have summarised these under the broader themes of digital competence, collaboration, communication, reflection, and self-guided learning. Creativity and innovation are often associated with work in digital media and were occasionally mentioned by EKT platform users; it was however the possibilities for collaboration (especially where collaboration had previously been difficult) which attracted the greatest approval of the EKT participants.

Through analysis of qualitative data generated at various stages in the project, this evaluation has also monitored evidence of impact on other professional competences relating to reflection. In focus groups, interviews, and open comments there are encouraging signs that working collaboratively in an online environment offers students accessible and efficient ways both to engage in reflection (though chat groups with staff and fellow students) and to store artifacts and refine their own thinking through the use of ePortfolios. It was not realistic to expect measurable shifts in self-reports of increases in reflective practice during a short placement, but there is sufficient evidence that the educational methodology and sound pedagogical principles embedded in the EKT platform and Small Private Online Course promote a reflective, action-research-based approach to teaching,

Working across professional and national boundaries to produce a placement platform and a Small Private Online Course has certainly helped to ensure that platform is accessible to a wide range of potential users and sensitive to an extended range of ethical considerations. This has been facilitated by the careful work on the well-received SPOC, which ensures that all users have a gradual introduction to the platform in a way that encapsulates sound pedagogical principles of reflective practice. Across all countries in the project, we have heard much about the demands on staff time and the stress that students are under, and this has motivated both education and industry partners to make the platform as efficient as possible. Working together on a complex project means we have learned a great deal about each other's strengths and specialisms, as well as some of the difficulties that characterise our work. Because the context in which initial teacher education happens is always changing, it is important to work with systems, tools and procedures which are adaptable. This places considerable demands on technological infrastructure and on the skills and aptitudes of all stakeholders, both to explain what is needed and then to turn these requests into a workable solution. During the course of the project, partners developed effective working relationships to seek to improve user satisfaction, develop professional competence and increase the quality of the products.

This EKT Project has been a success for all partners in the consortium, who achieved all outputs required of the initial proposal despite the challenges presented by the pandemic and school and university closures. All project partners look forward to working together again in future EU projects and look forward to adoption of the EKT Platform by interested parties, across Europe.

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7. APPENDIX A – EKT QUESTIONNAIRE (ENGLISH VERSION)

POST-COURSE SURVEY (ENGLISH)

* Required

A. Introduction

Dear participant,

This post-course survey is for the enrolled participants of the online course: “EKT Project”, organised by the Education Knowledge Transfer project (EKT Project) funded by European Union’s Erasmus+ KA2 - Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices.

The purpose of this survey is to evaluate the quality of the training sessions. Your responses will be considered by the course moderators to modify and upgrade the contents. Filling in the evaluation takes about 10 minutes.

Thank you very much for joining the EKT Project and participating in the evaluation.

Data handling:

The data from the questionnaire will be handled according to EU General Data Protection Regulation (2016/679). If you proceed with filling in the survey, you agree with how we handle the submitted data and agree that:

- Any information you provide will be anonymously stored and handled
- You have received adequate information about your participation in this survey

If you understand the information above and agree to continue with the survey, please tick the box below and proceed to the next section.

- I accept the terms and conditions above and agree to participate in the survey *
- I do not accept the terms and conditions of the survey and I would like to end my participation now.

B. Participant Profile

1. Country *

Choose (dropdown list)

2. Gender *

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to say

3. Age *

- 20-30
- 31-40
- 41-50
- 51-60
- 61-65
- 65+

4. Your Role

- Student teacher
- Academic mentor/tutor
- School mentor/tutor

5. For school mentor and academic mentor

Work Experience *

- 5 years or less
- 6-10 years
- 11-15 years
- 16-20 years
- Over 21 years

For student teachers:

- Bachelor degree Year 1
- Bachelor degree Year 2
- Bachelor degree Year 3
- Bachelor degree Year 4
- Master degree Year 1
- Master degree Year 2
- Other qualification (please specify)

C. Course Satisfaction

C1. Training Structure, Methods and Contents (MATRIX)

How satisfied are you with the following aspects of the training course? *

1 (*Very dissatisfied*) 2 3 4 5 (*Very satisfied*)

- Relevance of the training course learning objectives
- Relevance of the content covered by the course programme
- Training course timeline (frequency of asynchronous and synchronous activities; workload)
- Appropriateness of the activities presented
- Interaction and collaboration promoted between participants
- The online environment used to support the course
- Tutorial videos around the EKT System

C2. The EKT System (TSE Statements)

I am able to...

1 (strongly disagree) 2(disagree) 3 (neutral) 4(agree) 5(strongly agree)

- Use my knowledge of the EKT platform/tools to help my peers
- Adopt and adapt EKT platform/tools for assignments/school placement
- Integrate the EKT platform/tools into my placement work creatively
- Integrate the EKT platform/tools into my placement work with minimal help
- Search, evaluate and select appropriate technology resources within the EKT platform/tools
- Navigate the content of the EKT platform/tools
- Use the EKT platform/tools without being told how it works
- Use the EKT platform/tools when user manuals available
- Complete a job/task using the EKT platform/tools
- Complete a job/task using the EKT platform/tools if shown how to do it first.
- Use the Documents Tool: upload, create and share documents; work collaboratively in a document;
- Use the Calendar;
- Use the Communication Tool for private and group chats;
- Use the ePortfolio Tool

C3. Other Tools to support communication and reflection

- What other tools have you been using to communicate and support your peers?
- What other tools have you been using to reflect on your practice?

C4. Overall Satisfaction

Please answer the following questions:

- How could be the online course improved?
- How could be the EKT tools improved?

Thank you for your participation!

8. APPENDIX B – EKT FOCUS GROUP

FOCUS GROUP GUIDE

After the In-School placement experience, we are interested in your perceptions on the following issues on which we will discuss in the focus group:

- Perception of your preparation for ISP
- Perception about the possibility of having a technological platform such as EKT to share documentation and communicate (between student teachers, schools, university, mentors) during the ISP.
- Perception about the possibilities of technologies to improve the experience of ISP, what can it contribute?
- Reflection on the experience of ISP, use of the EKT platform and learning
- Perception of participating in an international educational research action

Thought-provoking questions **by topics are presented so that you can give a joint answer in each one attending to the different elements that arise**

ABOUT THE EKT PLATFORM

1. General assessment of the platform in terms of its difficulty of use. Has it been complex for you, in what?
2. Did you need more or less help before using the EKT platform?
3. Elements that should work better, why?
4. Advantages over the virtual campus of the university and disadvantages
5. What functionalities, tool and improvements you think should be implemented in the final version of the EKT system

ABOUT THE DIFFERENT FUNCTIONALITIES THAT HAVE BEEN INCLUDED IN THE INITIAL VERSION OF THE PLATFORM

TRAINING COURSE (EKT SPOC)

6. To what extent did you take the EKT training course?
7. Did it help you to familiarize yourself with the EKT platform and use it?
8. Did it bring you any interesting learning for the practices you were able to apply (reflection, observation, action research, etc.) Explain your response
9. Did you use the EKT e-portfolio? What is your assessment of this tool? Is it useful? For what?
10. 10. What elements should be improved in the EKT Eportfolio?

COMMUNICATION TOOL

11. Do you think it can be useful in practices to have a communication tool of this type?
12. In relation to others (Telegram, virtual campus forums, mail) what advantages do you see and what elements need to be improved?
13. In addition to the meetings convened by the academic mentors, did you use the tools of the EKT platform to communicate with others? If not, why not?
14. What advantages and disadvantages do you see with this tool?
15. What OTHER tools did you use to communicate with your mentors and peers?

CALENDAR TOOL

16. Do you think it can be useful in ISP? For what kind of situations?
17. Did you mark any events on the calendar? It was easy.?
18. If you didn't use it, why?

DOCUMENTS TOOL

19. Do you think it can be useful in practices to share documentation? What kind of information would be good to share?
20. Did you upload any files to the EKT platform?
21. Was it easy to share documents? Did you have difficulties? Which?

HELP TOOL

22. Did you go to this tool? If yes, what were you looking for? Was it helpful?
23. Would you add any kind of help not contemplated?

MANAGEMENT TOOL

24. Did you log in at some point? For what?
25. Do you see any use in practice?

COLLABORATIVE EXPERIENCE

26. Was it beneficial to have access to other student teachers and mentors through the EKT Platform?
27. Has the use of the EKT platform influenced your practices in any way?
28. The most positive and the most negative of the experience
29. Recommendations for the next piloting

9. APPENDIX C – ACCESS TO DATA COLLECTED FOR THE EVALUATION (WP 7)

Qualitative data

<https://cumulo.cesga.es/index.php/s/RQ2CTyQqo42BFCB>

<https://cumulo.cesga.es/index.php/s/83cP6PXc8isNjRk>

Quantitative data

<https://cumulo.cesga.es/index.php/s/oRKTs5ykBt8bXCF>

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